

Synthesis of 5-acylamino-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinones

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1-Cyanoethylpyrrole on reaction with N-chlorophthalimide provided 1-cyanoethyl-2-phthalimidopyrrole (3) that underwent cyclization by Hoesch reaction to give 5-phthalimido-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone (4), which on hydrazinolysis and acylation afforded the title compounds, 5-acylamino-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinones (1). The compounds 1 have been evaluated for their analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities.

It has been reported that 5-aminomethyl-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinones show significant analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities¹. Hence, 5-acylamino-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinones (1) were designed and synthesized, and their analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities were tested in mice.

We have reported the synthesis of the key intermediate, 5-amino-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone by reduction of 5-nitro-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone that was prepared by nitration of 1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone². It is difficult to separate three isomers produced on the nitration, and the yield was low. Thus, a new synthetic route of 5-amino-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone was designed. 1-Cyanoethylpyrrole (2) on reaction with N-chlorophthalimide provided 1-cyanoethyl-2-phthalimidopyrrole (3) by the reported procedure³ (Scheme 1). Compound 3 underwent Hoesch reaction to give compound 4, which was hydrazinolysed to afford 5 in good yields (Scheme 1). Compound 5 was readily acylated to give the title compounds 1.

Scheme 1

The compounds 1 were evaluated for their analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities by acetic acid-induced writhing in mice and by xylene-induced ear edema in mice⁴, respectively. Compound 1h displayed the highest analgesic activities and compound 1c and 1f exhibited potent anti-inflammatory activities. The activities of compound 1f and 1h were comparable to the activities of ibuprofen, the positive control.

Table 1. Analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities of compounds 1a-h (means \pm SD, $n = 10$)

Compd. no.	Dose (mg/kg)	Writhing count (n)	Inhibition (%)	Swell degree (mg)	Inhibition (%)
CMC-Na		46.0 \pm 20.7		16.0 \pm 4.7	
Ibuprofen	200	9.4 \pm 7.4**	79.6	10.4 \pm 3.2**	34.9
1a	200	28.0 \pm 23.5	39.1	10.6 \pm 5.8*	33.8
1b	200	28.4 \pm 23.1	38.3	10.2 \pm 5.7*	36.3
1c	200	19.1 \pm 9.7**	58.5	6.3 \pm 2.1**	60.6
1d	200	41.2 \pm 11.3	10.4	11.3 \pm 4.4	29.3
1e	200	15.7 \pm 14.6**	65.9	11.3 \pm 5.9	29.3
1f	200	16.4 \pm 7.4**	64.4	5.8 \pm 3.9**	63.7
1g	200	19.1 \pm 13.3**	58.5	9.6 \pm 4.2**	40.1
1h	200	12.6 \pm 10.4**	72.7	10.7 \pm 5.4*	33.0

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ compared with CMC-Na.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in capillary method, and are uncorrected. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker ARX-300 spectrometer and mass spectra on a GCMSQP-1000 instrument.

1-Cyanoethyl-2-phthalimidopyrrole (3) : To a solution of 1-cyanoethylpyrrole **2** (68.5 mmol) in CHCl_3 (250 ml) was added NaHCO_3 (137 mmol) in one portion. Then N-chlorophthalimide⁵ (68.5 mmol) was added to the mixture with violent stirring in small portions over a period of about 50 min. After addition, the mixture was stirred for 1.5 h, then filtered, washed with water (3×60 ml), and dried over anhyd. Na_2SO_4 . After removing the solvent, the resulting solid was crystallized from petroleum : THF (1 : 2), as a white crystals (41.6%), m.p. 170–172°; $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 2.79 (2H, t), 4.02 (2H, t), 6.21–6.89 (3H, m), 7.85 (2H, m), 7.98 (2H, m).

5-Phthalimido-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone (4) : Dried hydrogen chloride gas was passed into a mixture of **3** (10 mmol) in anhydrous THF 20 ml at 0–5° for 3 h. Then the mixture was allowed to stand overnight at 0–5°. The resulting solid was put into water (50 ml), and then the mixture was treated with 10% NaOH until pH 5.5. The mixture was refluxed for 40 min. It was then cooled and the resulting solid was crystallized from THF, as a white crystals (40%), m.p. 207–209°; $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 3.10 (2H, t), 4.27 (2H, t), 6.55 (1H, d), 6.85 (1H, d), 7.86 (2H, m), 7.99 (2H, m).

5-Amino-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone (5) : To a refluxed solution of **4** (3.7 mmol) in anhydrous ethanol (20 ml) was added dropwise 85% hydrazine hydrate (7.2 mmol) in anhydrous ethanol (3 ml). After the solution was refluxed for 30 min, it was then cooled and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to get a solid that was crystallized from anhydrous ethanol, (77%), m.p. 179–180° (lit.², m.p. 177–178°); $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 3.06 (2H, t), 3.74 (2H, br), 4.02 (2H, t), 5.78 (1H, d), 6.71 (1H, d); m/z 135 (M^+).

5-Acylamino-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone (1) : To a

solution of **4** (7.4 mmol) in pyridine (15 ml) at room temperature was added dropwise acyl chloride (8 mmol) in dried 1,2-dichloroethane (18 ml). The mixture was stirred at 40° for 3–6 h and extracted with 1,2-dichloroethane. The combined organic extracts was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and water, dried over anhyd. Na_2SO_4 , concentrated in vacuum. The resulting solid was crystallized from ethanol or purified by silica gel column chromatography. Eight of compounds **1** were prepared : **1a**, m.p. 199–201°, $\delta(\text{DMSO}-d_6)$ 3.00 (2H, t), 4.26 (2H, t), 6.52 (1H, d), 6.64 (1H, d), 7.58 (3H, m), 7.79 (2H, d), 10.65 (1H, s); **1b**, m.p. 204–205°, $\delta(\text{DMSO}-d_6)$ 2.40 (3H, s), 3.00 (2H, t), 4.25 (2H, t), 6.49 (1H, d), 6.63 (1H, d), 7.36 (2H, d), 7.87 (2H, d), 10.53 (1H, s); **1c**, m.p. 178–180°, $\delta(\text{DMSO}-d_6)$ 2.99 (2H, t), 3.85 (3H, s), 4.25 (2H, t), 6.48 (1H, d), 6.64 (1H, d), 7.08 (2H, d), 7.96 (2H, d), 10.45 (1H, s); **1d**, m.p. 178–181°, $\delta(\text{DMSO}-d_6)$ 2.55 (3H, s), 2.99 (2H, t), 4.25 (2H, t), 6.49 (1H, d), 6.64 (1H, d), 7.40 (2H, d), 7.92 (2H, d), 10.55 (1H, s); **1e**, m.p. 205–207°, $\delta(\text{DMSO}-d_6)$ 3.00 (2H, t), 4.26 (2H, t), 6.52 (1H, d), 6.64 (1H, d), 7.64 (2H, d), 8.00 (2H, d), 10.70 (1H, s); **1f**, m.p. 214–216°, $\delta(\text{DMSO}-d_6)$ 3.00 (2H, t), 4.26 (2H, t), 6.52 (1H, d), 6.64 (1H, d), 7.78 (2H, d), 7.91 (2H, d), 10.70 (1H, s); **1g**, m.p. 255–256°, $\delta(\text{DMSO}-d_6)$ 3.01 (2H, t), 4.28 (2H, t), 6.57 (1H, d), 6.66 (1H, d), 8.19 (2H, d), 8.40 (2H, d), 10.98 (1H, s); **1h**, m.p. 145–148°, $\delta(\text{DMSO}-d_6)$ 2.96 (2H, s), 3.70 (2H, s), 4.16 (2H, s), 6.48 (1H, s), 6.57 (1H, s), 7.29 (5H, m), 10.50 (1H, s).

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